

There is a Factor of “Delay”!

Machines are fast & efficient in their own ways. And humans do have random uncertainty factors and times. That creates two possible delay roles.

1. Propagation side Delay (PSD)

2. Execution side Delay (ESD)

~ **Propagation side delay**: In this we know the time quantum & be considered as buffer delay on any human or machine side. This is a general communication gap or translation part delay.

~ **Execution side delay**: In this we don't know how long the delay can last for actually getting executed.

***Key Question** :) At which extent we can calculate & Predict the delays. And what independent tasks can be done when delay is processed in the background (Preparation Areas, Independent task list etc..)

My decision basis :)

Question i asked: Machines are Fast actually very fast in their execution but they don't know what to do and humans know what to do and why as in their needs but have random uncertainties that causes delay in execution. So what can we do in the mean free/buffer time. And how can we make it more productive and can we calculate this delay occurrence to some extent in order to avoid it or plan though it?

